

Digital Governance and Farmer Participation: Challenges and Opportunities in Maharashtra

Sagar Bhausaheb Dongare¹

Asst.Prof Department of Geography (M.J. College
(Autonomous) Jalgaon)

Email Id:- sagardongare29@gmail.com

Prof. Dr. Vilas Vasant Patil²

Department of Geography, Shri Shahu Mandir
Mahavidyalaya Parvati, Pune

Abstract:

Digital governance has emerged as an important mechanism for improving agricultural administration and farmer participation in India. In the state of Maharashtra the digital platforms are increasingly used to deliver agricultural services like crop advisories, subsidies, crop insurance and disaster compensation. Initiatives such as AI-based agricultural advisory platforms and digital farmer databases aim to improve transparency, efficiency and accessibility of government services. For example, Maharashtra has introduced digital platforms providing multilingual advisory services to millions of farmers and integrating data related to soil, weather, and markets. However, the adoption of digital governance among farmers is uneven across the state due to geographical, socio-economic, and technological factors. Regions such as Vidarbha, Marathwada, and tribal areas of western ghat, Gadchiroli face challenges including low literacy, digital illiteracy, poor network connectivity, outdated technology, economic limitations, and lack of awareness about digital platforms. At the same time, digital governance provides significant opportunities for farmers by enabling easy access to government schemes, saving time, improving service delivery, and ensuring transparency in policy implementation. This paper examines the challenges and opportunities of digital governance in the agricultural sector of Maharashtra while considering regional and geographical variations. The study highlights how digital initiatives can strengthen farmer participation if issues related to infrastructure, digital literacy, and accessibility are addressed.

Keywords - Digital Governance, Farmer Participation, Maharashtra Agriculture, Digital Agriculture, Rural Development

Introduction

Agriculture plays a crucial role in the economy of Maharashtra employing a large proportion of the rural population. The state has diverse agro-climatic regions including Western Maharashtra, Vidarbha, Marathwada, Konkan, and North Maharashtra, each with different agricultural conditions and technological access with geographical variation. Digital governance refers to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) to deliver government services and enhance citizen participation. In agriculture sector the digital governance includes mobile applications, online portals, digital farmer databases, and satellite-based crop monitoring systems. Government initiatives such as AI-based advisory platforms digital crop monitoring, and

farmer identification systems aim to improve productivity and ensure better implementation of schemes. More than 22 lakh farmer IDs have already been created in Maharashtra under digital agriculture initiatives. Despite these efforts, several barriers limit farmers' participation in digital governance systems.

Objectives of the Study:-

- To identify role of digital governance among the farmers in Maharashtra
- To analyze the challenges faced by farmers in accessing digital governance services.
- To identify opportunities created by digital governance for farmer participation.
- To understand how geographical variations impact on digital governance

Methodology:-

This study is based on secondary data analysis including government reports, research papers, policy documents, and agricultural digital governance initiatives in Maharashtra. Data from government digital agriculture programs and scholarly studies were used to analyze challenges and opportunities.

Result and discussion:-

Challenges in Digital Governance:

1. Literacy: - Many farmers in rural Maharashtra have limited formal education, which makes it difficult to understand digital interfaces, online applications, and government portals. Literacy levels vary significantly across regions, especially in tribal areas of Nandurbar, Gadchiroli, and parts of Vidarbha. Many digital platform are with English media because of this the rural people are not literate in English

2. Digital Literacy: - Digital literacy refers to the ability to use smartphones, computers, and internet platforms. Many farmers lack the technical skills needed to operate mobile apps or online agricultural services. Studies show that only a small percentage of farmers actively use digital applications for agricultural decision-making.

3. Network Connectivity: - Network connectivity remains a major challenge in rural areas. Many villages in Vidarbha and Marathwada experience weak internet connectivity, making it difficult for farmers to access digital services or register for online schemes. Lack of reliable internet infrastructure limits the effectiveness of digital governance programs.

4. Outdated Technology and Device Limitations:- Many digital agriculture services require high-configuration smartphones or laptops. The small and marginal farmers often use basic mobile phones that cannot support advanced mobile applications. This technological gap restricts participation in digital governance platforms.

5. Economic Constraints: - Economic inequality among farmers also affects digital adoption. Purchasing smartphones, laptops, or data services can be costly for small farmers. Since a large proportion of farmers in Maharashtra operate small landholdings investing in digital technology is often considered unaffordable.

6. Lack of Awareness among Farmers:- Another major barrier is the lack of awareness about digital governance platforms and government schemes. Many farmers are unaware of online portals for crop insurance, digital land records, and subsidy applications.

Opportunities of Digital Governance in Maharashtra Agriculture

1. Easy Access to Services: - Digital platforms allow farmers to access government schemes, crop advisories, and market information through mobile phones. AI-powered platforms provide real-time information about weather, pest control, and crop management.

2. Time Saving:- Digital governance reduces the need for farmers to visit government offices repeatedly. Online registration, digital documentation, and direct benefit transfers save time and reduce administrative burden.

3. Fast Service Delivery: - Digital systems enable faster processing of applications such as crop insurance claims, disaster compensation, and agricultural subsidies. Digital damage assessment systems also speed up compensation for crop losses.

4. Transparency in Implementation: - Digital governance improves transparency in the distribution of government benefits. Online systems and digital records reduce corruption and ensure that subsidies and financial assistance reach the intended beneficiaries directly.

Geographical Variation in Digital Governance Adoption in Maharashtra:- Maharashtra state of India is very challenging to implement government policy cause the regional topographic variation:

Western Maharashtra:- This region has relatively better digital infrastructure, higher literacy rates, and greater adoption of agricultural technologies.

Vidarbha:- Vidarbha faces serious agricultural distress and technological gaps. Network connectivity issues and economic challenges limit digital participation among farmers.

Marathwada:- Frequent droughts and economic constraints affect farmers' ability to invest in digital technology.

Konkan Region:- Although literacy levels are higher, geographical barriers such as hilly terrain sometimes affect internet connectivity.

Hilly and Tribal Regions: - Tribal districts such as Gadchiroli and Nandurbar and hilly region like harishchandra, Balaghat, Satuda, Chikhaldara face the greatest digital divide due to limited infrastructure and low digital literacy.

Suggestions and Policy Recommendations:-

The study suggests several important measures to strengthen digital governance and enhance farmer participation in Maharashtra. The rural internet connectivity should be improved by expanding broadband infrastructure in villages so that farmers can easily access digital services and government schemes. Along with this, digital literacy training programs should be organized for farmers to help them understand and effectively use digital tools and online platforms related to agriculture. It is also important to develop simple and user-friendly mobile applications in the Marathi language so that local farmers can easily access agricultural information, market prices, weather updates, and government services. Also the government should provide affordable smartphones through subsidy schemes to ensure that even small and marginal farmers can participate in the digital ecosystem. Awareness programs should be strengthened through agricultural extension services to educate farmers about available digital platforms and their benefits. In addition, village-level digital service centres should be established to provide technical support and assistance to farmers, enabling them to access online agricultural services, apply for schemes, and participate more actively in digital governance.

Conclusion:-

Digital governance has the potential to transform agricultural administration in Maharashtra by improving service delivery, transparency, and farmer participation. However, several structural barriers such as literacy gaps, digital skills, connectivity issues, and economic limitations restrict farmers' access to digital platforms. Addressing these challenges through infrastructure development, training programs, and awareness campaigns can help bridge the digital divide between urban and rural areas. With inclusive policies and region-specific strategies, digital governance can play a significant role in strengthening the agricultural sector and improving the livelihoods of farmers across Maharashtra.

References:-

Aker, J. C. (2011). Dial "A" for agriculture: Using information and communication technologies for agricultural extension in developing countries. *Agricultural Economics*, 42(6), 631–647. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-0862.2011.00545.x>

World Bank. (2019). *Digital dividends: World development report*. World Bank Publications.
<https://www.worldbank.org>

Government of Maharashtra. (2021). *Maharashtra agriculture policy and digital initiatives report*. Department of Agriculture, Government of Maharashtra.
<https://krishi.maharashtra.gov.in>

Mittal, S., & Mehar, M. (2016). Socio-economic factors affecting adoption of modern information and communication technology by farmers in India. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 22(2), 199–212. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2014.997255>

Government of India. (2025). *Digital Agriculture Mission*.

Maharashtra Department of Agriculture. *MahaVISTAAR-AI Digital Advisory Platform*.

Studies on Digital Agriculture and Farmer Adoption in India.

Dongare, S. B. (2018). *Detection of agriculture area of Sangamner Tahsil from LISS-III satellite image using NDVI techniques*. In *Multidisciplinary Approaches of Remote Sensing & GIS* (Vol. 1, Issue 1, pp. 165–170). Current Global Reviewer. ISSN 2319-8648.